

Teachers' knowledge, implementation, universal design for learning, inclusive secondary schools

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ABSTRACT

Global educational practice has become a transformative approach in addressing the needs of learners with diverse needs. However, few schools are practicing universal design for learning (UDL) principles in the Nigeria education landscape due to several factors. The knowledge and implementation of UDL principles among teachers is essential in order to accommodate diverse learners, including those with disabilities. The UDL principles promote flexible techniques and learning materials, inclusive learning environment achievement, where all learners are privileged to achieve global best learning. Therefore, there is a need for all teachers to be knowledgeable about this global practice during their training or in-service training in order to align with global practice for accessibility and inclusivity in Nigeria educational landscape. This study examines teacher's knowledge and implementation of UDL principles among teachers in public inclusive secondary schools in Lagos State. The study employed a descriptive research design. Three research questions were raised to guide the study. 72 special education teachers were randomly drawn from four purposively selected inclusive secondary schools in Lagos state. A self-designed questionnaire titled "Teachers' Knowledge and Implementation of UDL Principles Questionnaire (TKIUDLP) with reliability coefficient of ($r=0.81$) was used for data collection. Data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics, including frequency count, mean and percentage. Findings revealed that teachers have little or moderate knowledge about UDL principles with a total mean of 2.71. It was also indicated that these teachers' implementation of UDL principles is partially done without a systematic procedure that necessitates expertise and training. The study revealed several factors that militate against implementation of UDL principles. The study recommended intense training and re-training for teachers, particularly special education teachers and emphasis should be geared towards strengthening teachers' understanding of UDL principles and its practical approaches.

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Introduction

Global educational practice has transformed the education landscape through a modern approach to accommodate learners with diverse needs, taking into consideration individual differences. The reality of diverse learners within the classroom craves for a modern designed instructional strategy that provides more access and inclusion for diverse learners, including learners with disabilities. The traditional learning approach had become obsolete and could not meet the growing modern global education system that is characterized by diverse learners with distinct diversity in cultural orientation, linguistic diversity and different learning styles coupled with the presence of learners with disability in the same classroom (Eze, 2020). To achieve global practice for all learners without any form of marginalization and exclusion, it is essential to adopt an educational approach that serves all learners appropriately and meet their diverse needs through inclusive settings. Despite the increasing adoption of universal design for learning (UDL) to effectively foster inclusive educational practice in Lagos state, most teachers struggle to achieve its implementation due to several contextual factors.

The concept of universal design for learning (UDL) is an educational framework that is designed to ensure that diverse learners including those with disability and those without disability have equal access to different instructional methods, learning environment and facilities that align with their needs in a classroom setting (Obidike & Eze, 2021; Al-Ishlah, et al., 2025). Universal design for learning has emerged as a n instructional approach that provides and promotes usage of multiple, flexible and learning strategies According to (CAST, 2018), UDL is defined as a set of educational principles for curriculum development that provide all learners with equal opportunity to learn by creating instructional goals, teaching strategies, learning resources, materials and assessment that align with individual appropriate

needs that promote a flexible and customized to meet individual needs. It focuses on accommodating diverse learning needs of all students through the provision of resource materials and flexible strategies for effective learning. With the failure of the traditional instruction method to meet the differential needs of learners with special needs, the UDL principles built on three basic domains, referred to as principles, work together as a learning approach to ensure equal educational opportunity in achieving meaningful, purposeful and knowledgeable learning outcomes.

These three principles are: multiple engagement, representation and action and expression (CAST, 2018). The first principle encourages teachers to provide students with various ways and avenues to engage with the learning materials. This principle provides multiple choices for students to access content which could be achieved through team work, interactive session, group and individual work. Engagement ensures full participation of students in the learning process, encourages social interaction and diverse learning styles satisfy different interests. Motivation and self-regulation (Olamide, 2021). The second principle, representation is defined as the planning, accessing and implementing the content of the curriculum using multiple sources of information such face-to-face presentation, visual, auditory method, digital material like text messages, captioning, graphic, videos and images (Obidike & Eze, 2021). This principle of representation ensures that information is conveyed through various channels like auditory and visual so as to accommodate diverse learning methods. Further, the third and last principle of UDL, action and expression, provides students with freedom to choose a preferred method to express their understanding and skills acquired through exposure to learning, either through written, verbal, practical demonstration or signed languages. UDL fills the gap created by the traditional method of learning and instruction by

putting into consideration wider scope of engagement, representation and expression of knowledge and ideas of each learner in a unique way that aligns with their learning style.

Teachers impact knowledge and skills to students to enhance their capabilities and bring out the best in them through quality instructions that meet their education needs. Teachers nowadays, are saddled with greater responsibility to align with the current trend of global learning approach which encompasses a wider concept of engaging, representation and expression to meet the needs of learners with diverse abilities and learning style. Thus, teachers should gear up to meet up with the challenges of global learning for all learners so as to ensure inclusivity. The global educational principles of UDL is meant to create and sustain effective learning in a classroom with diverse learners, different abilities and different learning styles. Teachers are to adequately engage students in learning tasks, providing them with varieties of options to help them access the content of the curriculum. Students' self-engagement in interactive sessions with peer groups, collaboration discussion and exchanging ideology help students' participation in the learning process. Teachers are to offer multiple sources of representation that encompasses both visual and auditory (Capp, 2017). Almeqdad et al (2023) observed that UDL principles is an ideal professional approach that fosters positive practical engagement of teachers and builds healthy professional relations, emphasizing its uniqueness in creating inclusive environments that support diverse learners, particularly those with disabilities.

According to the Center for Exceptional Children (CEC, 2005), UDL recognizes and promotes the inclusion of learners (children and adults) with diverse learning challenges and offers guidelines for effective engagement of these learners to address their respective needs. The presence of students with diverse needs in the same classroom

necessitate the need for a well-experienced teacher vast in different teaching strategies and modification of the curriculum to suit the learning expectation of a wide range of students which include, the slow learner, average learners and the gifted and talented. Teachers found in this type of inclusive setting must possess the knowledge and expertise of impacting knowledge and skills to these diverse learners. Based on the foregoing, it is essential that teachers acquire the relevant knowledge through comprehensive training in UDL. Further, findings have shown that most teachers in inclusive settings lack the necessary knowledge about various disabilities and are confused on how to engage diverse learners with disability and those without disability which pose great difficulties as a result of behavioural challenges that many students with disability displayed in classroom (Nwogu, 2021)

Research findings revealed a level of awareness and understanding of universal design for learning among teachers who are well-trained and exposed to modern technology. According to Almurairi (2023), teachers showed great interest in adoption and use of flexible instructional materials and developing mindset of equity, and learner-centered teaching approach to meet the needs of diverse learners, however, they lack the capacity to generate con. In the same vein, a study conducted in Lagos state reported that the majority of teachers in both regular schools and inclusive schools lack the necessary skills to effectively apply UDL principles in their teaching technique due to inadequate knowledge and training. Westine et al (2019) emphasized the need to enhance effective training strategies to promote understanding of universal design for learning principles so that instructors can provide more inclusive teaching strategies that facilitate inclusivity. The researchers underscore the importance of promoting awareness and understanding of universal design for learning and its adoption in creating an inclusive educational system for all learners.

The implementation of UDL principles in daily classroom' activities involves engagement, representation and expression of learnt content. The incorporation of digital technology in providing multiple means of engagement and representation cannot be overemphasized. Teaching and learning processes to meet students' diverse needs necessitate the use of multiple strategies. Multimedia resources are alternative to traditional assessment and evaluation. Students are to be introduced to technological devices that present information in different forms. In this case. The role of technology cannot be undermined with its tremendous capability to help learners understand concepts through presentation of multiple techniques. Technology provides avenues for multiple tasks, easy access to content through diverse means and enhances active engagement and participation in the learning process (Eze, 2020). Technology does not only facilitate presentation of information in various ways like videos, text, images, written and audio, but also provides a platform for diverse engagement simultaneously. Students are exposed to varied options that facilitate learning. While the hearing students focus on audio presentation, visual presentation also provides practical understanding. The deaf learners become more curious to learn as a result of various means of information. The deaf child has privilege to sign, maximize visual captioning and engage in flexible learning approach through technology

In a study by Almutairi & Alsuwayi (2023), conducted in Saudi Arabia to determine the level of knowledge of 225 elementary school teachers on universal design for learning (UDL). It was found that the teachers have a moderate level about UDL, revealing that female teachers have higher knowledge about UDL than their male counterparts. Further, the researchers noted that teacher's knowledge is an essential variable that assures the effective implementation of universal

design for learning (UDL) principles which requires more skills and experience that teachers must possess. Eze (2020) observed that the implementation of UDL principles in Nigeria is still emerging, emphasizing the fact that implementation of UDL is partially done with reference to supporting inclusive practice. The author highlighted that visual aids and other simplified instructional materials are often adopted to support learners with special needs in inclusive settings but these are not systematically applied in planning and assessment due to contextual factors in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Global learning strategies have transformed the educational landscape with tremendous efforts in addressing the needs of diverse learners in the classroom. The UDL principles aim to remove barriers and promote effective engagement of diverse learners to have access to equal learning opportunities, regardless of their age, gender, culture, and disability. Several studies have focused on the adoption of UDL to enhance academic performance of learners with little focus on current awareness and implementation of UDL principles in order to promote inclusive education in Lagos state, Nigeria. Further, most of these studies are conducted in tertiary institutions while there are few at the secondary school on teachers' knowledge and implementation of UDL principles which is essential in promoting inclusive learning in secondary schools. With fewer schools practicing inclusive education in Lagos state, about 13 inclusive secondary schools and 33 inclusive primary schools (Lagos State Ministry of Education, 2023), adoption of UDL principles will no doubt promote inclusive learning and accommodate more students with disabilities within their neighborhood in secondary schools. Thus, this study deals with how UDL principles could facilitate inclusive educational practice for learners with special needs and examines teachers

'knowledge and implementation of UDL principles in inclusive secondary schools in Lagos state.

Purpose of the Study

This study aimed to specifically examine:

1. Teachers' knowledge about UDL principles in inclusive secondary schools in Lagos state.
2. Whether teachers implement UDL principles in inclusive secondary schools in Lagos state.
3. Challenges facing implementation of UDL principles in inclusive secondary schools.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the teachers' level of awareness of UDL principles in inclusive secondary schools in Lagos state?
2. Do teachers in inclusive secondary schools implement UDL principles?
3. What are the challenges militating against the implementation of UDL principles in inclusive secondary schools in Lagos state?

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design to examine teachers' knowledge and implementation of UDL principles in inclusive secondary schools in Lagos state. The population comprised all teachers in inclusive secondary schools in Lagos state. Four inclusive secondary schools located in Ikeja, Surulere, Agege and Badagry educational zones were purposely selected from the 13 inclusive secondary schools in Lagos state for convenience. These schools are: Ikeja grammar school (Inclusive unit), Ikeja; Sango secondary school (Inclusive unit), Ikeja; Lagos state grimmer school (Inclusive unit), Surulere and Methodist high school (Inclusive unit). Badagry. 72 teachers were drawn through total enumeration from the inclusive unit of the selected secondary schools to participate in the study. The researcher

sought permission to conduct a research from the zonal education offices. With the letter of permission, the researcher was granted access to administered the questionnaire to the teachers in the four inclusive sampled schools for the study. Data was collected using a self-designed questionnaire titled "Teachers' Knowledge and Implementation of UDL Principles Questionnaire (TKIUDLPQ)", with a reliability coefficient ($r=0.81$). The instrument is divided into four sections: section A, which seek for demographic information: section B, solicit for Teachers' knowledge about UDL principles section C, address the implementation of UDL principle and Section D, make inquiry on challenges facing implementation of UDL principles in Lagos state. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics which involves frequency count, percentage, mean and standard deviation. A five-point lilac rating was used with: 5 for Strongly Agree = SA, 4 for; Agree = A, 3 for Neutral = N, 2; Disagree = D, 1 for Strongly Disagree = SD

Result

The sample size for the study was 72 special education teachers. Among the 72 teachers, 56 of them representing 77.8 % were female and 16 (22.2%) were male teachers. This implies that there were more female sign language teachers than the male teachers. Furthermore, 47 corresponding to 65.3% sign language teachers had first degree certificates; 6.9% of them had NCE certificates; while 22.2% and 5.6% of the teachers had PGDE and Masters Degree certificates respectively.

Answering Research Questions

Three research questions guided this study.

Research Questions 1

What is teachers' level of awareness of Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles in inclusive secondary schools in Lagos State? To answer this question, the data collected were subjected to descriptive statistics of simple counts, mean and

standard deviation. The summary of the result of descriptive statistics of simple counts, mean and standard deviation is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Teachers' Level of Awareness of Universal Design for Learning (UDL) Principles in Inclusive Secondary Schools in Lagos State

Statement	N	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	SDev.
I am aware of Universal Design for Learning (UDL)	4	25	34	6	3	1.71	.863
UDL is a global learning educational system that provide principles to promote equal access to diverse students	1	26	33	7	5	1.85	.883
I am not familiar with the UDL principles	3	1	7	33	28	3.14	.954
UDL principles are not necessary to improve inclusive practice in schools	8	1	3	35	25	2.94	1.29
There are three principles of the UDL. These engagement, representation and expression	8		1	39	24	2.99	1.169
UDL principle involves the use of multiple means of engagement through varieties of strategies	5			53	14	2.99	.911
UDL principle provides multiple means of information to students through multimedia approach	6		2	50	14	2.92	.989
Students are not offered opportunity to express understanding of concepts in various ways	3		4	43	22	3.13	.855
Awareness of Universal Design for Learning Principles (Grand Mean = 2.71; SDev. = .979)							

Keys: Strongly Agree = SA; Agree = A; Neutral = N; Disagree = D, Strongly Disagree = SD

Decision Rule: If Mean is ≤ 0.49 = Neutral; 0.5 to 1.49 = Strongly Disagree; 1.5 to 2.49 = Disagree; 2.50 to 3.49 = Agree; 3.50 to 4.0 = Strongly Agree.

Special education teachers were asked to respond to their level of awareness of Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles in Table 1. The result showed that the special education teachers had moderate awareness about the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles in inclusive secondary schools in Lagos State, mean = 2.71; standard deviation = .979 on a scale of 5. The agreement to the awareness of Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles is evident in their claim that they are familiar with the UDL principles (mean = 3.14; standard deviation = 0.954); UDL principles are necessary to improve inclusive practice in schools (mean = 2.94; standard deviation = 1.209); aware of the three principles of the UDL: engagement, representation and expression (mean = 2.99; standard deviation = 1.169); UDL principle involves the use of multiple means of engagement

through varieties of strategies (mean = 2.99; standard deviation = 0.911); UDL principle provides multiple means of information to students through multimedia approach (mean = 2.92; standard deviation = 0.989); students are not offered opportunity to express understanding of concepts in various ways (mean = 3.13; standard deviation = 0.855).

Research Questions 2

Do teachers implement Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles in inclusive secondary schools in Lagos State? To answer this question, the data collected were subjected to descriptive statistics of simple counts, mean and standard deviation. The summary of the result of descriptive statistics of simple counts, mean and standard deviation is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Implementation of Universal Design for Learning (UDL) Principles in Inclusive Secondary Schools in Lagos State

Statement	N	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	SDev
They make sure they prepare an individualized educational plan for my students based on required accommodation	3		1	40	28	3.25	.852
They used digital tools in the classroom to display vital information, definition, transcription and translation	5		3	44	20	3.03	.978
They make sure that content of lessons is available in various form e.g visual, audio tape, video, sign languages	4	1	1	51	15	3.00	.888
They encourage students to engage in various tasks that interest them	3		2	50	17	3.08	.81
They provide students with various options to demonstrate and share their understanding of content/topics	1		1	51	19	3.21	.64
They ensure active participation of student in diverse strategies in classroom using discussion, interactive, group and individual practice	1		2	45	24	3.26	.65
They always ensure that all barriers to learning in the classroom are removed and students learn at their pace	1	1	1	48	21	3.21	.67
Implementation of UDL Principles (Grand Mean = 3.15; SDev. = .777)							

Keys: Strongly Agree = SA; Agree = A; Neutral = N; Disagree = D, Strongly Disagree = SD

Decision Rule: If Mean is ≤ 0.49 = Neutral; 0.5 to 1.49 = Strongly Disagree; 1.5 to 2.49 = Disagree; 2.50 to 3.49 = Agree; 3.50 to 4.0 = Strongly Agree.

Special education teachers in inclusive secondary school units were asked to state whether or not they implement the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles in Table 2. The special education teachers agreed that they implemented the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles in inclusive secondary schools in Lagos State, (mean = 3.15; standard deviation = .777 on a scale of 5. This assertion is indicative in their responses such as: they make sure they prepare an individualized educational plan for their students based on required accommodation (mean = 3.25; standard deviation = 0.852); they used digital tools in the classroom to display vital information, definition, transcription and translation (mean = 3.03; standard deviation = 0.978); and they make sure that content of lessons is available in various form e.g visual,

audio tape, video, sign languages (mean = 3.00; standard deviation = 0.888). Other reasons to assert that the UDL principles are implemented include: they encourage students to engage in various tasks that interest them (mean = 3.08; standard deviation = 0.801); they provide students with various options to demonstrate and share their understanding of content/topics (mean = 3.21; standard deviation = 0.604); they ensure active participation of students in diverse strategies in classroom using discussion, interactive, group and individual practice (mean = 3.26; standard deviation = 0.650) and they always ensure that all barriers to learning in the classroom are removed and students learn at their pace (mean = 3.21; standard deviation = 0.670).

Research Questions 3

What are the challenges militating against the implementation of Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles in inclusive secondary schools in Lagos State? To answer this question, the data collected were subjected to descriptive statistics of

simple counts, mean and standard deviation. The summary of the result of descriptive statistics of simple counts, mean and standard deviation is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Challenges Militating against the Implementation of Universal Design for Learning (UDL) Principles in Inclusive Secondary Schools in Lagos State

Statement	N	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	SDev.
Insufficient resources	1		1	36	34	3.42	.666
Lack of training	2		1	44	25	3.25	.746
Culture and regional differences	1		4	50	17	3.14	.635
Nigeria Educational system	1		3	49	19	3.18	.635
Policy and regulatory framework		1	2	49	20	3.22	.562
Lack of knowledge on curriculum modifications	3		1	54	14	3.06	.767
Unavailability and lack of exposure to technology in the school	2		2	54	14	3.08	.687

Challenges militating against the implementation (Grand Mean = 3.19; SDev. = .671)

Keys: Strongly Agree = SA; Agree = A; Neutral = N; Disagree = D, Strongly Disagree = SD

Decision Rule: If Mean is ≤ 0.49 = Neutral; 0.5 to 1.49 = Strongly Disagree; 1.5 to 2.49 = Disagree; 2.50 to 3.49 = Agree; 3.50 to 4.0 = Strongly Agree.

Special education teachers were asked to identify challenges militating against the implementation of UDL principles in inclusive secondary schools in Lagos State. Sign language teachers agreed that there were challenges militating against the implementation of UDL principles, (mean = 3.19; standard deviation = .671 on a scale of 5 as indicated in Table 3. Such challenges include: insufficient resources (mean = 3.42; standard deviation = 0.666); lack of training (mean = 3.25; standard deviation = 0.746); culture and regional differences (mean = 3.14; standard deviation = 0.635); Nigeria Educational system (mean = 3.18; standard deviation = 0.635); policy and regulatory framework (mean = 3.22; standard deviation = 0.562); lack of knowledge on curriculum modifications (mean = 3.06; standard deviation = 0.767 and Unavailability and lack of exposure to technology in the school (mean = 3.08; standard deviation = 0.687).

Discussions of findings

Teachers' knowledge of Universal Design for Learning in Inclusive Secondary Schools in Lagos State

The findings of this study revealed that teachers of learners with special needs in inclusive secondary schools in Lagos state have moderate knowledge about UDL principles. This was indicated with a mean score of 2.71. The findings of this study concur with the work of Almutairi & Alsuwayi (2020), the authors observed that teachers of elementary schools in Saudi Arabia have appreciable knowledge about universal design for learning (UDL) principles. However, contrary to this study, Mavrovic-Glaser (2017) reported that teachers have little or no knowledge of UDL principles which is associated with lack of training. In the same vein, it was revealed that facilities that align with teaching and practice of UDL principles are not available, thereby creating a huge barrier to

effective learning and full participation of learners with hearing impairment in inclusive secondary school Lagos state. The study further buttressed the fact that provision of strong UDL strategies is bound to fail if it is not accessible to special needs students, particularly those with hearing impairment. In an assessment carried out by a foundation known as Festus Fajemilo (FFF) in the 44 inclusive public schools, including public secondary and primary schools in Lagos state. It was revealed that the majority of the teachers in the inclusive unit teaching learners with special needs lack the knowledge and capacity to collaborate effectively in universal design for learning (UDL) principles which fosters inclusive education. Further, the findings buttressed the fact that most of these inclusive schools lack well-trained special teachers which makes it difficult for them to professionally adopt UDL principles.

Implementation of Universal Design for Learning Among Special Education Teachers in Inclusive Schools in Lagos State

The findings of this study show that special education teachers implement UDL principles indicating a mean average of 3.25. This could be attributed to the fact that individual teachers who responded might engage learners effectively through application of some UDL strategies by presenting various teaching materials that match a special student's needs and depends on the personal experience of the teacher. However, the findings of this study negate the findings of this study which agrees with the study of Eze (2020) who observed that teachers in Nigeria often support inclusive education practice through an ornamented approach by providing differential and remedial education. However, the researcher emphasized that adequate implementation of UDL goes beyond provision of multimedia and involves proactive curriculum design. Further, findings of this study negate the findings of Adeosun and Akinyemi (2020), the researcher reported that the implementation of UDL principle is done at peripheral level without thorough systematical

approach. The researcher highlights the fact that teachers tend to adopt peer tutoring, low-tech engagement, limited assessment options and re-teaching techniques instead of intentional and structured lesson redesign to accommodate all learners with diverse needs.

Challenges Militating Against Implementation of Universal Design for Learning

The findings of this study revealed that special education teachers encountered various challenges in implementation of universal design for learning principles. The study revealed that several challenges such as insufficient resources, lack of training, cultural and regional variables, lack of access to technology, policy regulatory framework and the country's educational system pose great challenges on the implementation of UDL principles in inclusive secondary schools in Lagos state. The findings align with the study of Olagunju & Oyewunmi (2022) who noted that contextual variables, including poor access and unavailability of technology, lack of varied assessment alternative, lack of training and rigid curriculum are some of the factors militating against implementation of UDL principles in Lagos states inclusive secondary schools. This study also corroborates with the submission of (CAST, 2018; Almutain, & Alsuwayi 2023; Morenikeji et al, 2022), these authors posit that that professional development of teachers is an essential factor that pose as barrier against implementation of UDL principles, emphasizing the fact that training, collaboration, adequate time planning and classroom monitoring and evaluation promote and sustain implementation of UDL. Moreover, the finding of this study corroborates with Adegbite & Oshodi (2024). The researchers noted that while adoption of UDL instructional principle fosters and promotes inclusivity in schools for learners with special needs, its implementation is faced with enormous challenges such as lack of resources, teacher's preparedness, professional development and educational policies.

Conclusion

This study revealed the current state of teachers' knowledge about UDL principles, its implementation and challenges in inclusive secondary schools in Lagos state. Though there was moderate knowledge of UDL principles among teachers, the implementation of UDL principles still remains partial with inadequate consistency. The implementation of UDL principles was highly confronted with several factors ranging from lack of professional development to inadequate resources. Acquisition of adequate knowledge and full implementation of UDL principles deserved strengthening teacher's potentials through capacity building, exposure to practical modelling and provision of information and communication technology instructional materials.

Recommendations

- Teachers should be enthusiastic and remain motivated in acquiring skills through professional development programmes. Teachers should endeavor to engage in continuous learning and personal development programmes to enhance effective teaching.
- The government should ensure adequate monitoring of implementation of UDL principles in inclusive secondary schools to foster inclusivity. Special education officers are to enforce compliance with UDL standards.
- Adequate funding and provision of special equipment, instructional materials, assistive devices and technology-driven devices should be prioritized to full implementation of UDL principles.
- All stakeholders in the education sector should form a synergy through collaboration in order to tackle major challenges confronting implementation of UDL principles in inclusive secondary schools in Lagos state.

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